

CONNECTING THE LED LIGHTING SYSTEM TO AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM TO CONTROL THE LEVEL OF LIGHT IN THE ROOMS

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Abstract: Based on existing technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan recent studies have shown that energy-efficient LED lighting systems provide better visual comfort and room or building works in an absolutely harmless way to the environment with low energy consumption compared to existing lighting systems. Today, daylighting systems have a technological scheme capable of this we will be able to regulate and monitor light intensity through communication technologies using smart sensors. The purpose of this article is to present the implementation of Led energy-saving lights and information about the installation of a modern, economical and efficient LED lighting system scheme that uses various energy-saving techniques without disturbing the visual comfort of passengers. The proposed lighting system scheme uses ZigBee and Wi-Fi communication systems protocols to control commercial/residential lights in all areas as well. Usually natural daylight, occupancy or building occupants' requirements lead to excessive light consumption in buildings. Illumination the system can work in three different modes: we will be able to set it up based on manual, automatic and hybrid system to account for different applications. Wireless sensor and actuator network (WSAN) is used to collect existing data on the use of personalized state-of-the-art LED lights. The article presents studies on the complete design and implementation of a modern lighting system. This paper also presents the implementation of detailed test experiments of the proposed state-of-the-art lighting technique and data management system and in the proposed technological system, the energy consumption of the lighting system and the visual light effect of the passengers were studied. Invited the lighting system aims to reduce energy consumption by 50% compared to the existing lighting system provides visual comfort of passengers. The proposed pilot study also offers guidance on incorporating intelligence into such a system, it can automatically predict passenger preferences in a decentralized system for better visual comfort and improvement.

Keywords: Lighting system, LED light, wireless sensors, actuator networks, technical database management system, automatic control scheme

Introduction

Today, the automation of devices and systems based on modern technologies is gradually changing the lives of ordinary people. Devices based on modern technologies and technological systems are well advanced due to the introduction of Internet of Things (IoT). Like today's modern devices and technological systems Smarter than previous studies, modern buildings now use the latest technological advances. In most areas in the Republic of Uzbekistan modern technologies are widely used. In modern buildings, devices are automatically and intelligently controlled and in the building creating many advantages for residents. Modern LED lighting system is an important part of smart building as a lighting tool. Modern lighting system implements technological processes of automatic or semi-automatic light control and light intensity adjustment methods. A modern lighting system can also consist of LED lights. controlled using the same control system. The use of daylight makes the lighting system more economical. The main purpose of a modern lighting system is to illuminate people for movement at night. A modern lighting system takes into account several parameters, including the available natural light. The proposed state-of-the-art lighting system involves the design of a wireless sensor actuator network (WSAN). Technological system includes ZigBee wireless communication between sensors and actuators. LED automatically changes the lighting according to individual preferences and connects to the network via Wi-Fi. The proposed lighting system is a decentralized system. The central server collects the sensor values through the coordinator and the user and the technological performance of private agents favors efficiency. A JAVA agent runs on a central server to store the collected data and in the formation of the database, work is carried out on the basis of the scheme. Data collection is done at certain time intervals. Modern technology tools are used to obtain the estimated values of the actuator for automatic control of light intensity for visual comfort. in the Republic of Uzbekistan using these advanced technologies, a new framework for controlling lights is presented within this study and will consist of light distribution in a smart building based on the personal preferences of the occupants and natural daylight. Visual comfort depends not only on it it works depending on factors such as environmental factors, as well as user requirements and expectations, modes.

Modern lighting system design and lighting control processes

The framework proposed in this paper allows to change the brightness of lights to provide satisfactory visual comfort of lighting and lower energy costs for users. In addition, the framework provides a methodology for combining visual

comfort and in the built environment, there will also be opportunities to connect devices to WSNs. The scheme of the proposed WSN framework can scatter light as shown in Picture 1. To account for different types of experiments (with individual control and centralized control). the frame will be designed to work in three different modes. Manual mode - users can interact with the lights and according to their wishes, the light is distributed or automatically changed from one type to another. Automatic mode setting - In a special technological system, lights operate according to model-based or data-based control. Indicators of light scattering based on sensor measurements. Hybrid mode - we change to a mode where the lights can turn on automatically, but users can interact and when feeling discomfort, the effect of light intensity together with the device is reduced by a certain amount. Modern two-way communication networks can monitor the activity of sensors and then put them into active maintenance mode it creates opportunities to obtain and control information from them. Therefore, the modern lighting system is designed using WSN. A WSN structure includes the following. of light each node passing to nodes representing an autonomous entity in the network. The network of sensors in this system it consists of sensor nodes that transmit the measured sensor values to the coordinator. The effect of light makes the knot easier and accelerates the connection of WSN with other nodes connected to it. The startup scheme works based on the instructions. The lighting system performs the suggested actions. Technological focusing on the preferences and circumstances of individual users to manage the system. The view of the room lighting system is shown in Picture. 1.

Picture 1. Lighting lamps currently used in the Republic of Uzbekistan (the photo was taken in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Nukus city, Amir Temur Street, 105, house 79. Author: Otelbayev Azizbek, student of the Nukus Mining Institute).

Modern lighting system test experiments

Experiments are being developed at test sites and the modern lighting system is being tested on a large scale. The test area consists of: shows how to change the room lighting. Lighting levels can be set by the user using sliders and is an application based on a modern technical system on a mobile phone or desktop, which has the ability to control it for each user depending on his position. The test area consists of a voltage-controlled SrCoO₂ film that can be electronically controlled to limit or change it. During the day taking into account the amount of natural daylight entering the room, the light decreases its activity. There is also a remote controlled roller shutter can reduce room lighting by 50% when turned on. This manual system application is also available automatically changes the brightness of the room. Picture 2 (a) shows the components of the sensor node, and Picture 2 (b) shows the schematic of the actuator. Light control in the technological system implements technological processes in connection with all its components, respectively. The actuator automatically detects and changes the brightness of the LED depending on the sensor nodes of the system. In the system the output signal and the signal received from the coordinator are monitored and connected to one system (main system). The coordinator controls the control algorithm and maintains it. The light of the room should be directed to the specified point. The test area is shown in Picture 2 (c).

Picture 2. Controlling the distribution of light in the room and transferring it to the control mode based on the technological system.

Conclusion

For this article, the results of the research on the implementation of the Smart LED lighting system and effective data management system are presented. Currently, one of our main goals is to create visual comfort for the residents of modern buildings. The proposed lighting system uses ZigBee multi-storey Wi-Fi connection to control the lighting of their buildings according to the naturally

existing conditions daylighting can be done according to the requirements of the residents of the residence or building, which will reduce the consumption of excess electricity by up to 50%. There may be a lighting system works in three different modes: manual, automatic and based on hybrid systems to account for different applications. Wireless sensor and actuator network (WSAN) is used to collect existing data on the use of adaptive smart LED and we will have to calculate the number of lights and how many volts the lights work on by the people living in the building. The article also includes a detailed implementation of the proposed test area state-of-the-art lighting techniques and data management system to demonstrate the effect of the proposed lighting system our main goal is to satisfy the energy consumption and visual requirements of passengers, to create advantages. The results show when the recommended lighting system when applied, the lux values fall within the recommended illuminance range throughout the test area. We need to plan for the future will be to enhance the capabilities of the proposed system in terms of self-study of user preferences and accuracy. Currently, Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute, is conducting research on the optimization of the technological management processes of lighting systems and the control of the system in automated mode.

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